

Supplementary Documentation

Moonwatching dates.

Spring: April 28, 2018; April 29, 2018; April 30, 2018; April 21, 2019; April 21, 2019; April 22, 2019; May 20, 2019; March 6, 2020; March 8, 2020; May 06, 2020; May 08, 2020; March 27, 2021; March 28, 2021; March 29, 2021; March 30, 2021; April 25, 2021; May 25, 2021; May 26, 2021.

Fall: September 18, 2018; October 22, 2018; October 23, 2018; October 23, 2018; August 29, 2020; August 30, 2020; August 31, 2020; September 3, 2020; September 4, 2020; September 20, 2020, October 3, 2020; October 5, 2020.

Flight path extraction workflow.

The analysis workflow for extracting migratory bird information from the video involved several steps, which are summarized below. Honeycutt and Bridge (2022) provide a detailed account of the data extraction process. All analyses were done in the R programming environment (R Core Team 2021) and relied heavily on computer vision tools available in the Rvision package (Garnier and Muschelli 2022), which is a wrapper for the OpenCV library (Bradski 2000). We made use of the adaptive thresholding functions in Rvision to identify dark pixel clusters (henceforth referred to as contours) in each frame of video. The contours identified by this process included both bird silhouettes and considerable noise associated with camera movement and dark features on the moon. We applied filtering based on recurrence of dark pixel

clusters in the same locations to remove contours that were likely craters on the moon, and we ranked contours according to how distinct they were from the immediate background (more distinct contours were more likely to be bird silhouettes).

Next, we attempted to assemble contours into linear series of points across a sequence of video frames. Each contour was compared with all contours from three previous and three subsequent frames to find potential linear combinations. If a series of at least three contours was detected that met a threshold for linearity, the search for contours was extended forward and backward in time to add to the flight path. Any contours added to a flight path were flagged such that they could not contribute to another flight path. The results of this step yielded a data set that contained mostly real flight paths (based on further data filtering and visual inspection), but instances where paths were assembled from false contours were frequent. We first removed false detections by examining linearity of contours, number of contours comprising a path, and distinctiveness of contours; most false contours were eliminated by filtering on these parameters. To further ensure the removal of false paths, we visually inspected sets of video frames associated with paths that were questionable as indicated by low contour counts, reduced linearity, and faint contours. We also visually inspected distinct contours that were not linked to a flight path to ensure that we did not fail to detect any birds.

Simulation of the effect of moon angle on group detection

A complicating factor in the analysis of moonwatching data is the fact that the volume of air that is effectively sampled by moonwatching changes with the angle of the moon relative to the horizon (henceforth the moon elevation angle). When the moon elevation angle is low (e.g. 20 degrees), the cone of observation defined by the circumference of the moon and the location

of the observer encompasses a larger volume of the lower atmosphere than when the moon is at a higher elevation angle (e.g. 70 degrees; see Supplementary Figure S1). Moreover, when the moon is full or nearly so, moon elevation angles are generally greater in the middle of the night than they are near sunset and sunrise, which means that, depending on flight direction, there can be a strong bias on the absolute numbers of birds detected at different times of night. This effect of moon elevation angle was noted in Lowrey's description of moonwatching along with the

geometrical calculations that allow one to adjust estimates of bird passage rates to account for moon elevation angle (Lowrey 1951). By quantifying group migration as proportions of all birds detected (as opposed to absolute bird counts or rates of detection) we may largely ignore the problems associated with sampling across different moon elevations. However, at relatively high moon elevation angles, the less oblique cone of observation

Supplementary Figure S1. Illustration of the relationship between moon elevation angle and the sampling volume available for moonwatching observations. Note that the drawing is not to scale--the moon has been enlarged and its distance from the ground shortened for illustrative purposes. As moon elevation angle increases, moonwatching samples a smaller volume of airspace in the lower atmosphere. At any given altitude (e.g. the horizontal line drawn above ground level), the horizontal ellipse that a bird flies through (assuming flight is parallel to the ground) is much more elongated at low moon elevation angles (note the red lines associated with moon angles of 15° and 75°).

would make it more likely for us detect only one member of groups that fly near the edge of the moon while other group members flying outside the observation cone would be missed.

To obtain a rough estimate of the degree to which moon elevation angle affects detection of groups, we devised a simple computer simulation of 10,000 birds flying across a section of sky that included the cone of observation defined by the moon. One thousand (10%) of the birds were designated as pairs and they were separated in space by a random draw of distance values that came from the mean and standard deviation of our observed data from groups of birds. For simplicity, we assumed a uniform height of 1000 m above the ground, and we specified that all birds were flying perpendicular to the long axis of the ellipse defined by the planar section of the cone of observation. We built this simulation in R (R Core Team 2021) and ran it 100 times each for moon elevation angles from 15° to 75° in 15° intervals. The code used to execute the simulation is available on the Open Science Framework: <https://osf.io/bv5hj/>.

This simulation indicated that the effect of moon elevation angle on detection of group migration was likely quite small. Although the simulation revealed a large difference in total birds detected across moon elevation angles (6,082 detections at a moon elevation angle of 15° vs. 403 detections at an angle of 75°; Table S1), the percentage of pairs detected changed relatively little with moon angle (9.87% at a 15° angle vs. 8.36% at a 75° angle; Table S1). Moreover, we note that this simulation was based on a worst-case scenario wherein birds would be flying broadside relative to the point of observation as opposed to toward or away from the observer. Hence, we are led to conclude that the overnight pattern we observed during spring migration is largely due to actual changes in behavior as opposed to sampling limitations.

This conclusion is also evinced by examining moon elevation angles associated with our spring bird detections across the nighttime octiles. There is an expected pattern wherein moon elevation angles peak in the middle of the night, but there is also considerable variation around this pattern, which is associated

Table S1. Results from a simulation of moonwatching detections across a range of moon elevation angles. Values on each line of the table are means from 100 simulations at each elevation angle. Each simulation entailed 10000 virtual birds, with 1000 or 10% of them situated as members of a pair.

Moon Angle	Detection Range	Total Detections	Percent in Groups
15°	13500 pix	6747	9.87
30°	3600 pix	1800	9.53
45°	1800 pix	900	9.09
60°	1200 pix	602	8.42
75°	964 pix	482	8.36

with the range of moon phases during which video footage was collected (Fig 2). In addition, the nighttime pattern in moon elevation angle across octiles does not closely mirror the pattern of group behavior in the spring. Specifically, the octile with the highest median moon elevation angle (54.5 degrees in octile 4) does not have the lowest percentage of birds in groups. Rather, the group percentage for octile 4 in the spring is intermediate (4.2%). Also, the springtime

percentage of birds in groups for octile 6 is low to intermediate (3.0%) even though the mean moon angle for this octile (38.6 degrees) is about the same as in octiles 1, 2, and 3 (33.2, 37.5, and 42.8 degrees respectively), wherein the

percentage of birds in groups was 8.0% or higher (see Fig 1). Hence, we conclude that although moon elevation angle may have some effect on detection of groups, this effect does not account for the overnight pattern of group behavior we observed.

Literature Cited

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